

Parental Involvement and Academic Performance among College Students: Basis for a Program Plan

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Regie G. Divinagracia

DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
Regie.divinagracia@dmc.edu.ph

Jovie S. Furton

DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
jovie.furton@dmc.edu.ph

Norilyn S. Lirasan

DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
norilyn.lirasan@dmc.edu.ph

Esterlita T. Lumanda

DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
esterlita.lumanda@dmc.edu.ph

Maria Nova D. Ortiz

Faculty, School of Teacher Education
DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
maria.ortiz@dmc.edu.ph

Nelson A. Cordova Jr.

Program Head, School of Teacher Education
DMC College Foundation, Inc., Fr. Patangan Road, Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0939-2899> | nelson@dmc.edu.ph

Abstract

This study aimed to seek the relationship between perception of parental involvement and academic performance. The study utilized quantitative-correlational approach through surveys conducted to the selected non-medical college students in DMC College Foundation Inc. Several adapted questionnaires were used to gather necessary data for the study. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship between variables. After data gathering, it was found out that majority of the respondents in DMCCFI were females and 19 to 20 years old, and the respondent parents were college graduate and has an income that ranges from P 15, 001 to P 20, 000. It is also found out that the level of parental involvement at home of the respondents were involved based on the 10 indicators while, the level of parental involvement at school of the respondents were neutral based on the 7 indicators. The result unveiled that the parental involvement at home has a mean of 3.90 which means that they were involved while the parental involvement at school has a mean of 3.19 which interprets to neutral involvement, the overall assessment of the level of parental involvement is interpreted as involved with a mean score of 3.55. The results of academic performance of the respondents reveals a mean of 4.41 which can be described as strongly agreed and interpreted as excellent in performance based on the 8 indicators. It was determined that there was no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance of the respondents.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Parental Involvement, DMC College Foundation, Inc.

Introduction

Parental involvement in monitoring their children's academic progress and its impact on their academic achievement cannot be overemphasized. It has gained significant attention from educators, teachers, curriculum developers, and school administrators as they are determined to find ways to improve the academic performance of students. Nowadays, parents' involvement in monitoring their children's academic progress is increasingly becoming one of the most effective ways of ensuring good standards and practices of education. It is therefore a global concern among parents to be fully aware of their children's activities in school and how best they can support them to improve the quality of education (Ayimbila et al, 2022).

Academic performance refers to how students deal with their studies and how they accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers (Banquil et al, 2009). It also refers to how students deal with their studies and how they cope with different factors affecting their performance. Rienties et al. (2011) stated that the academic performance of students is defined as the outcome of their studying process and the final result of their academic effort during their education. Academic achievement of a student is not only determined by his scholarly ability or mental talent, but also it is distinguished by a student's motivation to fulfill his academic aims, trying to attain his academic goals, and feeling satisfied with the academic environment. Academic performance is considered an important achievement for students during the educational process at the university. The achievement of the performance affects the students' current and future life (Kell et al., 2013), as well as portraying students' inherent productivity and ability (Hanushek, 2020; Sothan, 2019).

Parental involvement in a child's education has long been recognized as a significant factor in shaping academic outcomes. The level of parental involvement encompasses a range of activities, including but not limited to, helping with homework, attending parent-teacher conferences, volunteering at school, and engaging in educational activities at home. Numerous studies have explored the relationship between parental involvement and academic performance, seeking to understand the extent to which parental engagement impacts students' educational outcomes.

A considerable body of literature suggests that parental involvement positively influences various aspects of academic performance. For example, a meta-analysis conducted by Fan and Chen (2001) found a significant correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement across various cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds. Similarly, a longitudinal study by Hill and Tyson (2009) revealed that consistent parental involvement was associated with higher standardized test scores and graduation rates among high school students.

Moreover, research has highlighted the importance of different forms of parental involvement. For instance, involvement in school-based activities, such as attending parent-teacher meetings and participating in school events, has been linked to improved academic performance (Desimone, 1999). Additionally, active engagement in students' learning at home, such as monitoring homework completion and providing academic support, has shown positive effects on academic achievement (Epstein & Van Voorhis, 2001).

However, while the literature generally supports a positive association between parental involvement and academic performance, the nature and strength of this relationship may vary depending on several factors. These factors may include the child's age, cultural background, and socioeconomic status, as well as the specific types of parental involvement considered (Hill et al., 2004).

Numerous studies have explored the intricate relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement, aiming to understand how varying levels of parental engagement impact students' educational trajectories. The importance of parental involvement in education is underscored by its potential to mitigate the adverse effects of socio-economic disparities and other challenges faced by students Pinantoan, A. (2013). Research has consistently shown that students with involved parents tend to perform better academically, exhibit higher levels of motivation, and demonstrate improved behavioral outcomes compared to their peers with less parental support (Hill Ne, Craft SA 2003). Moreover, parental involvement has been linked to enhanced cognitive and socio-emotional development, laying the foundation for long-term academic success and positive life outcomes.

However, the level and nature of parental involvement can vary significantly across different families and cultural contexts. While some parents may actively engage in their child's education by attending parent-teacher conferences and volunteering at school, others may face barriers such as language barriers, lack of time due to work commitments, or limited access to educational resources. Understanding the diverse factors that influence parental involvement is crucial for developing targeted interventions and policies aimed at fostering collaboration between families and schools to support student achievement.

Through this research, the researchers hope to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on parental involvement in education and inform educational practices and policies aimed at enhancing student achievement and closing achievement gaps. By elucidating the role of parental involvement in shaping academic performance, the researchers aim to empower stakeholders to implement evidence-based strategies that foster a culture of partnership between families and schools, ultimately benefiting the educational experiences and outcomes of all students.

This study sought to determine the significant relationship of Parental Involvement and Academic Performance among college students of DMC College Foundation Inc. Moreover, this study is guided by the following objectives: To determine the level of parental involvement among college students. To examine the impact of parental involvement on students' academic performance. To provide recommendations for intensifying partnerships between the school and the parents of the students, and to craft a comprehensive program plan based on the findings of this study.

This study also intends to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Economic Status
 - 1.4. Educational Background
2. What is the level of the parental involvement among the respondents?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents during the 1st semester of school year 2023-2024?
4. Is there a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance of the students?

Literature Review

Parental Involvement

Parental involvement is known to be the blend of dedication and active contribution paid by parents for their child (Jethro & Aiva, 2012). Lack of concurrence has witnessed parental involvement due to the definition of this construct, and despite its intuitional meaning, the functional use of parental involvement has not been clear and consistent (Wilder, 2014). Explanations given by researchers vary in their different interpretations; further, the study suggests that parental involvement is "the dedication of resources by the parents to the child within a given domain" (Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1994). Also, a few other researchers define "family involvement can be generally defined as the parents or caregivers' investment in the education of their children" (LaRocque, Kleiman, & Darling, 2011). Being narrower than one that views parental involvement as "parents' behavior in the home and school setting means to support their children's educational progress" (El Nokali, Bachman, & Votruba-Drzal, 2010).

In contrast, parent-child communication deals with a continuous discussion between parent and their children regarding school-related activities and his/her academic concerns (Shute, Hansen, Underwood, & Razzouk, 2011). It also refers to parents talking to their children about things they have done in school, i.e., results of their tests, presentations, projects, or their academic progress as a whole (Caro, 2012). It also supports the idea of parents taking time out from their busy schedule and spending it with their child to talk to them. Parents, through talk, ask their children whether they are facing any problems in school regarding their studies and try to solve them.

Parental involvement corresponds to many constructs of school, such as engagement, which includes attending parent-teacher conferences, contributing to extracurricular activities, monitoring student grades, imparting parental values,

helping with homework, and providing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. However, Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) noted that schools have failed to engage parents fully.

According to the Centre for Child Well Being (2023), parents' involvement in their child's learning process offers many opportunities for success, and it not only improve child's morale, attitude, and academic achievement across all subject areas, but it also promotes better behavior and social adjustment. It further says that family involvement in education helps children to grow up to be productive, responsible members of society. This means that if we involve the parents in educating their children, it is tantamount to saying that the school is proactive in implementing changes or development among students. As parent's involvements is increased, teachers and school administrators also raise the chance to realize quality reform in education.

Parental involvement offers opportunities for parents and teachers to create mutual respect and understanding (Owen, 2018). (Epstein, 2018), also posited that parental involvement in education helps teachers to acquire a better understanding of the family's culture and diversity, and from deeper respect for parents' abilities and time. Effective involvement of parents in their children's education has a positive effect on their children's lives, including their development, behavior, motivation, and academic performance (Dann, 2020). Involving parents in their children's education enables their wards to understand the importance of education and pursue it to the highest level. Parental involvement is parental intervention in their children's education in order to be able to obtain information about their children's academic growth, participation, when they define parental involvement (Crozier, 1999). "Family and community involvement frequently means helping reach goals defined by the schools (administrators and teachers) that reflect only school values and priorities" (Jordan et al., 2001, p. 10).

In order to explore parental involvement among low-income families, a case study was conducted at a public elementary school in the Pacific Northwest. In 2002, a new school replaced an outdated structure. During the planning stage for the new school, community members and agency professionals, along with educators, developed and implemented programs to both support families and engage them in their children's education. The study found that the development and implementation of intentional parental involvement strategies positively influenced the level of parental involvement. In addition, participants perceived numerous benefits to students and families resulting from strategies implemented and the related involvement. Parental involvement strategies also influenced educators. (Smith,2006).

Academic Performance

Educational achievement is said to be one of the major achievements in life. Academic performance is considered the basis for selection for higher education and jobs. It is supposed to bring about and contribute towards the prosperity, happiness, satisfaction, and well-being of the individual. Researchers and policymakers have long known that family background is an important determinant of success in school. A well-rounded family and stable environment are most likely to give a child a positive future and influence. Parental involvement is an awareness of schoolwork, understanding of the interaction between parenting skills and students' success in schooling. (Thomas, 2023)

On the other hand, students' academic performance is a critical feature of education. Generally, academic achievement is the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals. Several indicators can be used to determine the academic performance of the students, of which grades are the most common and essential (Farooq et al., 2011). There are various factors from which we can determine the academic performance of students. Studies have shown a variety of aspects, inside as well as outside of the classroom, including curricular and extracurricular activities. Studies have two kinds of performances. The first one is on-going students' academic performance, and the other one is collective students' academic performance. Both include some specific components of learning that ultimately count as a full academic performance of students. The classroom participation during ongoing assessment by a teacher in the form of question-answer on one base, group task, and involvement within group tasks, homework, and other such projects, which require ongoing assignment, comes under the ongoing students' performance (Farooq et al., 2011).

Relationship of Parental Involvement and Academic Performance

The linkage of parental involvement can be determined from this early childhood education of the students, and there, the involvement is considered to be very high. Parents are expected to be more concerned for their children during their early years of schooling. Indeed, much of the research has demonstrated that the strength of the relation between parental involvement in a child's education declines as the child grows older. During primary education, a child moves towards autonomy and self-dependency resulting from its surroundings, teachers, peer interactions, curricular choices, classroom experiences, and family attachment. There is less attachment as compared to the early years of his schooling (Li & Fischer, 2017). But researchers like Lumen (2020) widely accepted that parents play a significant role in their child's education, and now there is comprehensive research literature that shows that parental involvement is beneficial for children and adults alike (Lumen, 2020).

Cheung (2019) argues that Poor parenting has therefore been found to be of actual concern. Keith (1992). However, critiques of poor parenting have quickly transformed into criticism of poor parents, reproducing negative images of working-class families. Kalayci & Oz (2018) say that many Researchers have highlighted that governing the ideas of good parenthood mostly derive from middle-class perspectives. While some middle-class parents think that their children will have educational success and are confident in their own ability to influence their children's future, if necessary, others, whose condition means that success is less taken for granted, demonstrate a more strategic orientation.

Gonzalez-DeHass et al. (2005) argued that when parents are involved in their children's schools, academic motivation and achievement increase. Students' interest in learning, competence, and understanding of a subject area, improves and promotes student achievement. Haas and Reiley (2008) examined ways to increase homework completion among middle school students using selected interventions.

Haas and Reiley also found that not all students knew how to fill out the homework planners accurately, and the increased communication with parents served to improve these students' organizational skills and increase homework completion rates.

The No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act of 2001 (U.S. Department of Education) indicates that parents have a considerable role in promoting the academic achievement of their children. Regardless of this legislation, schools should and are encouraged to strengthen their efforts in developing innovative ways to involve parents in their children's academic growth. Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) noted that the duty of a school to promote parental involvement has become a passive act, rather than a genuine effort. In addition, parents are often scapegoats when trying to find the blame for student achievement. For example, some educators blame parents for the children's academic failures (e.g., "If only the parents helped at home" or "Parents just don't care about school"). Despite these remarks, research continues to credit parental involvement as a way to increase academic achievement effectively. Studies show that parents are, in fact, a strong independent variable in motivating their children to learn (Gonzalez-DeHass, 2005; Williams & Holbein, 2005).

Educational researchers have long been interested in the positive effect that parental involvement may have on the academic achievement of their children (Fan & Chen, 2001). The perception that parental involvement has positive effects on students' academic achievement has led to a voluminous body of literature about parental involvement (Hill & Tyson, 2009; Jeynes, 2003; Patall, Cooper, & Robinson, 2008). Policymakers and researchers seem to have agreed that parental involvement is a critical ingredient for children's academic success (Graves & Brown Wright, 2011; Mattingly, Prislun, McKenzie, Rodrigues, & Kayzar, 2002). Parents who are active participants in their children's education are thought to promote children's social, emotional, and academic growth (Green, Walker, Hoover-Dempsey, & Sandler, 2007).

According to Jensen and Minke (2017), parent engagement in education has been shown to have positive effects on students' academic and social/emotional success. However, much of the research has focused on younger students. Less attention has been given to parent engagement at the secondary level, especially with respect to how parents choose to engage and how adolescents perceive this engagement. This article reviews the literature on parent engagement at the secondary level, focusing on its importance to academic achievement, high school completion rates,

and socio-emotional functioning. Factors influencing parents' decisions to become engaged are discussed, including parental self-efficacy, role construction, and specific invitations from the child. Parent engagement remains important at the secondary level, though parent behaviors appear to change to match the developmental needs of students. Implications for practice and future research are discussed.

For many years, educators, parents, and social scientists have conceptualized engaged parents as those who help their children with their homework, frequently attend school functions, and maintain household rules that dictate when their young engage in schoolwork and leisure. Recent meta-analyses on parental involvement confirm the salience of more subtle social variables, which Bandura and Walters asserted may be even more important than overt parental behavior in fostering positive student outcomes. These results indicate that factors such as parental expectations, the quality of parent-child communication, and parental style may be more highly related to student achievement than various more overt expressions of this involvement. (Jeynes, 2010).

A multiple mediation model indicated that the child's perception of cognitive competence fully mediated the relation between parent involvement and the child's performance on a standardized achievement test. The quality of the student-teacher relationship fully mediated the relation between parent involvement and teacher ratings of the child's classroom academic performance. Limitations, future research directions, and implications for public policy initiatives were discussed. (Topor, Keane, Shelton and Cal-Kins, 2010)

Parental participation has a positive impact on students' academic success. Family and community have a vital influence to students' learning (Erdem & Kaya,2020; Roy & Girado-Garcia,2018). There is no consensus about a standard definition of parental involvement in education, given that it is a multidimensional concept involving various parental practices and behaviors regarding students' education and learning processes. Parental involvement in this study refers to the amount of active and meaningful participation of biological parents, both financially and behaviorally, in children's learning at home and school. Epstein's research (as cited in Smokoska, 2020) asserts that parental involvement has four components: parenting, communicating, learning at home, and participation in decision-making. Parenting is the process of assisting families in establishing a supportive environment at home via knowledge of child development, expertise in child and adolescent care, and the creation of an environment that encourages learning in children of all ages and grade levels. To communicate is to develop open lines of communication on student progress and educational initiatives between parents and the school.

Musgrave (2000) argues that students who come from an educated home would like to follow the steps of their family and, by doing so, work actively in their studies. Jeynes (2002) also avers that a child from a well-educated family with high socio-economic status is more likely to perform better than a child from an illiterate family. He suggests that children from an educated family are seen to have lots of support, such as a decent and good environment for academic work, parental support and guidance, enough textual and academic materials, and decent feeding. Eamon (2005) again claims that virtually in all nations, children of parents high on the educational, occupational, and social scale have a far better chance of getting into good secondary schools and from there into the best colleges and universities than equally bright children of ordinary workers or farmers. In fact, the most important factor associated with the educational achievement of children is not race, ethnicity, or immigrant status; instead, the most critical factor is parents' involvement (Considine & Zappala, 2002).

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative correlational design since the research sought to answer leads to numerical data. Specifically, the study was descriptive as it determined the level of parental involvement on the academic performance of College Students of DMC College Foundation Inc. and assessed whether the degree of impact of these variables was significant.

The respondents in this study were the non-medical college students who came from the departments of the School of Business Accountancy, College of Computer Studies, School of Teacher Education, and School of Hotel, Restaurant and Institution Management, who were officially enrolled in the second semester of school year 2023-2024. The researchers utilized the Slovin's sampling formula in order to get the number of respondents from the total population which is 145.

The research instrument utilized for this study was adapted from the work of Quijano et al. (2023) entitled Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Grade 12 Students. This questionnaire was modified to fit the context of the study then, a pilot test was done to ten students from the medical programs.

The instrument was divided into three parts. Part one is the consent form, wherein respondents checked if they allowed the researchers to use the data that they provided. Part two is on respondents' demographics, specifically with the respondents' age, gender, economic status of their parents, educational background of their parents, and the persons involved in their education. The third part of the instrument was the statements on parental involvement, which were divided into two parts: (A) Parental Involvement at Home and (B) Parental Involvement at School. The last part of the instrument was on the academic performance of the respondents using the academic performance scale.

In order to analyze the data, various statistical tool was used: (A) Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution. This statistical tool is used to determine the number of respondents who answer a particular rating. After determining the frequency count, the percentage distribution will also be utilized to determine the degree as to which a characteristic occurs. (B) Weighted Mean. The weighted mean is used to measure the responses of the respondents. (C) Standard Deviation. Standard deviation is used to provide an indication of how far the individual responses to a question vary or deviate from the mean or how spread out the responses are of our respondents, and (D) Person Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The Pearson-r correlation is used to measure the significant relationship between variables. For this particular study, parental involvement and academic performance among college students, to see if it has a significant relationship.

The researchers observed ethical demeanor in conducting the entire study. For the gathering of data, the researchers made sure to send a letter to the Department Deans and advisers prior to the conduct of this study. Upon approval, the researchers proceeded to data gathering through surveys. For the adapted questionnaires, the researchers ensured giving credits and proper citation to its authors and references. Most importantly, the researchers ensured that utmost confidentiality was observed. Data and information gathered from the respondents was treated with privacy and the gathered data will be disposed properly after analysis and interpretation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Counts	% of Total
19 y/o- 20 y/o	25	39.7 %
21 y/o-22 y/o	24	38.1 %
23y/o-24y/o	9	14.3 %
25y/o-26y/o	2	3.2 %
Above 26 y/o	3	4.8 %
TOTAL	63	100%

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The data shows that 25 or 39.7% of the respondents are 19 to 20 years old while 24 or 38.1% are 21 to 22 years old. Furthermore, 9 or 14.3% are 23 to 24 years old, 2 or 3.2% are 25 to 26 years old and 3 or 4.8% are above 26 years old. This finding signifies that majority of the respondents are 19 to 20 years old.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Counts	% of Total
Male	25	39.7 %
Female	38	60.3 %
TOTAL	63	100%

Shown in Table 2 are the profile of the respondents in terms of gender. As shown in the table, 25 or 39.7% of the respondents were males, while 38 or 60.3% were females with a total of 63 respondents. This finding means that the majority of the students were female.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Economic Status of Parents

Economic Status of Parents	Counts	% of Total
P 15, 001 – P 20, 000	18	28.6 %
P 20, 001 – P 25, 000	7	11.1 %
P 25, 001 – P 30, 000	3	4.8 %
P 30, 001 – P 35, 000	8	12.7 %
P 35, 001 – P 45, 000	8	12.7 %
P 45, 001 and above	7	11.1 %
TOTAL	63	100%

Table 3 displays the profile of the respondents in terms of Economic Status/Income of Parents. As revealed in the table, 18 or 28.6% of the respondents have an economic income of the parents that ranges P 15, 001 – P 20, 000, while 8 or 12.7% of the respondents have an equal count of economic income of the parents that ranges P 30, 001 – P 35, 000 and P 35, 001 – P 45, 000. Furthermore, 7 or 11.1% of the respondents have an equal count of economic income that ranges P 20, 001 – P 25, 000 and P 45, 001 and above. This finding means that the majority of the respondent parents income ranges from P 15, 001 to P 20, 000.

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Background of Parents

Educational Background of Parents	Counts	% of Total
Elementary Level	2	3.2 %
Elementary Graduate	2	3.2 %
High School Level	3	4.8 %
High School Graduate	6	9.5 %
College Level	17	27.0 %
College Graduate	29	46.0 %
Master's Level	4	6.3 %

Doctoral Level	0	0.0%
TOTAL	63	100%

Table 4 disclosed the profile of the parent/s respondents in terms of educational background. As revealed in the table, an equal count of 2 or 3.2% of parents of the respondents were elementary level and elementary graduate while 3 or 4.8% were high school level and 6 or 9.5% were high school graduate. Furthermore, 17 or 27% of the parents were college level, 29 or 46% were college graduate, 4 or 6.3% attained master's level/degree and none of the respondent reached doctoral level. This finding means that the majority of the parent respondents were college graduate.

Table 5. Level of Parental Involvement at Home

INDICATORS	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
My parents talked about school happenings.	4.08	0.85	Agree	Involved
My parents asked about my school progress.	4.03	0.80	Agree	Involved
My parents helped me develop a good study habit.	3.75	1.11	Agree	Involved
My parents impose strict rules when it comes to school matters.	3.59	1.13	Agree	Involved
My parents encouraged me to get good grades.	4.27	0.85	Strongly Agree	Highly Involved
My parents are the one paying for my school fees.	4.33	0.92	Strongly Agree	Highly Involved
My parents give me enough money for school projects and requirements.	4.27	0.92	Strongly Agree	Highly Involved
My parents scolded me whenever I got low or failing grades.	2.92	1.24	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral
My parents give me rewards if I got high grades.	3.43	1.15	Agree	Involved
My parents seemed to be proud of me when I do well in school.	4.38	0.87	Strongly Agree	Highly Involved
OVERALL ASESSMENT	3.90	0.58	Agree	Involved

Table 5 exhibits the level of parental involvement of the respondents at home. Using a 5-Likert scale adopted from Quijano, et. Al. (2023) with 1-being not involved, 2-slightly involved, 3-being neutral, 4-being involved and 5 -being highly involved. The outcome manifests that the respondent parental involvement at home were "highly involved" in the 4 out of 10 indicators; My parents encouraged me to get good grades (Mean= 4.27, SD=0.85); My parents are the one paying for my school fees (Mean= 4.33, SD=0.92); My parents give me enough money for school projects and requirements. (Mean= 2.92 SD=1.24); My parents seemed to be proud of me when I do well in school. (Mean= 4.38, SD=0.87). Furthermore, the result unveiled that the respondent parental involvement at home were "involved" in the 5 out of 10 indicators; My parents talked about school happenings (Mean= 4.08, SD=0.85); My parents asked about my school progress. (Mean= 4.03, SD=0.80); My parents helped me develop a good study habit. (Mean= 3.75, SD=1.11); My parents impose strict rules when it comes to school matters. (Mean= 3.59, SD=1.13); and My parents give me rewards if I got high grades. (Mean= 3.43, SD=1.15). Moreover, 1 indicator; My parents scolded me whenever I got low or failing grades (Mean= 2.92, SD=1.24); shows neutral in parental involvement at home. Overall, the parental involvement at home disclosed with a mean of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 0.58 which can be described

as agree and interpreted as involved based on the 10 indicators. This finding entails that the level of parental involvement at home of the respondents were involved.

Table 6. Level of Parental Involvement at School

INDICATORS	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
My parents attend school conferences/meetings.	3.33	1.24	Agree	Involved
My parents attend school events (e.g. Founding Anniversary, Pasiklaban)	2.59	1.41	Disagree	Slightly Involved
My parents show support for my extracurricular activities.	3.84	1.21	Agree	Involved
My parents monitor my school performance by reaching out to our coordinator/dean.	2.97	1.28	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral
My parents allow me to attend school activities (fieldtrips, retreats, clean-up drives).	4.08	1.07	Agree	Involved
My parents receives communication from school (e.g. emails, teacher updates).	2.86	1.29	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral
My parents go with me to school during enrollment.	2.63	1.47	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral
OVERALL ASESSMENT	3.19	0.82	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral

Table 6 exhibits the level of parental involvement of the respondents at school. Using a 5-Likert scale adopted from Quijano, et. al (2023) with 1-being not involved, 2-slightly involved, 3-being neutral, 4-being involved and 5 -being highly involved. The result presents that the respondent parental involvement at school were “involved” in the 3 out of 7 indicators; My parents attend school conferences/meetings. (Mean= 3.33, SD=1.24); My parents show support for my extracurricular activities. (Mean= 3.84, SD=1.21); My parents allow me to attend school activities (fieldtrips, retreats, clean-up drives). (Mean= 4.08, SD=1.07). Furthermore, the result unveiled that the respondent parental involvement at school were “neutral” in the 3 out of 7 indicators; My parents monitor my school performance by reaching out to our coordinator/dean. (Mean= 2.97, SD=1.28); My parents received communication from school (e.g. emails, teacher updates). (Mean= 2.86, SD=1.29); My parents go with me to school during enrollment. (Mean= 2.63, SD=1.47). Moreover, 1 indicator; My parents attend school events (e.g. Founding Anniversary, Pasiklaban) (Mean= 2.59, SD=1.41); shows slightly involved in parental involvement at school. Overall, the parental involvement at school revealed with a mean of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 0.82 which can be described as neither agree or disagree and interpreted as neutral in involvement based on the 7 indicators. This finding entails that the level of parental involvement at school of the respondents were neutral.

Table 7. Level of Parental Involvement

INDICATORS	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AT HOME	3.90	0.58	Agree	Involved

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AT SCHOOL	3.19	0.82	Neither Agree or Disagree	Neutral
OVERALL ASSESSMENT	3.55	0.65	Agree	Involved

Table 7 shows the level of parental involvement of the respondents with the combined mean of parental involvement at home and parental involvement at school. Using the same scale range of parental involvement (Figure 1), the result unveiled that the parental involvement at home with a mean of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 0.58 which interpreted as involved based on the 10 indicators while the parental involvement at school with a mean of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 0.82 which interpreted as neutral in involvement based on the 7 indicators had an overall assessment of the level with a mean of 3.55 and a standard deviation of 0.65 which described as agreed and interpreted as involved. This result entails that the level of parental involvement of the respondents were involved.

Table 8. Academic Performance

Indicators	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENT	INTERPRETATION
I made myself ready in all my subjects.	4.78	0.58	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance
I pay attention and listen during every discussion.	4.89	0.364	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance
I want to get good grades in every subjects.	4.94	0.25	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance
I actively participate in every discussion.	4.70	0.59	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance
I start papers and projects as soon as they are assigned.	4.57	0.61	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance
I enjoy homework and activities because they help me improve my skills in every subject.	3.94	0.69	Agree	Good Performance
I exert more effort when I do difficult assignments.	3.79	0.74	Agree	Good Performance
Solving problems is a useful hobby for me.	3.73	0.72	Agree	Good Performance
OVERALL ASESSMENT	4.41	0.30	Strongly Agree	Excellent Performance

Table 8 displays the level of academic performance of the respondents. Using a 5-Likert scale adopted from Quijano, et al (2023) with 1- Failing Performance, 2- Poor Performance, 3- Moderate Performance, 4 Good Performance and 5 - Excellent Performance as the highest level. The result presents that the respondent academic performance was excellent in performance in the 5 out of 8 indicators; I made myself ready in all my subjects. (Mean= 4.78, SD=0.58); I pay attention and listen during every discussion (Mean= 4.89, SD=0.364); I want to get good grades in every subjects. (Mean= 4.94, SD=0.25); I actively participate in every discussion. (Mean= 4.70, SD=0.59); and I start papers and projects as soon as they are assigned (Mean= 4.57, Sd=0.61). Furthermore, the result unveiled that the respondent's academic performance was good in performance based on the 3 out of 8 indicators; I enjoy homework and activities because they help me improve my skills in every subject (Mean= 3.94, Sd=0.69); I exert more effort when I do difficult assignments. (Mean= 3.79, Sd=0.74); solving problems is a useful hobby for me (Mean= 3.73, Sd=0.72). Comprehensively, it revealed with a mean of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 0.30 which can be described as strongly agreed and interpreted as excellent in performance based on the 8 indicators. This finding implies that the academic performance of the respondents was excellent.

Table 9. Test of relationships between Parental Involvement and Academic Performance.

	Pearson's r	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT	-0.093	61	0.467	Not significant/ weak negative correlation	Fail to reject
and					
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE					

Level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 9 displays the correlation between parental involvement and academic performance. Utilizing the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r), the result yields to r- value of 0.032 and p-value of 0.912 with the significance level of 0.05. The r- value (-0.093) asserted that there was a weak negative correlation between parental involvement and academic performance. Since the p-value (0.467) is greater than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$), this finding implies that there was no significant correlation parental involvement and academic performance.

Thus, the null hypothesis, H_0 : There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance **was accepted**.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this investigation, it was concluded that the majority of the respondents from DMCCFI were female and belonged to the age group of 19 to 20 years old. Most of their parents were college graduates with a monthly income ranging from ₱15,001 to ₱20,000. The study revealed that the level of parental involvement among the respondents was classified as involved, while their academic performance was rated as excellent. However, statistical analysis showed no significant correlation between parental involvement and the academic performance of the respondents. As a result, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between these two variables, was accepted.

In light of the findings and conclusions, the researchers recommend that the school develop targeted interventions and programs that encourage greater parental involvement and foster stronger partnerships between home and school. It is also advised that the school consider adopting the comprehensive program plan proposed by the researchers to further enhance student support. Additionally, the implementation of mentorship programs where teachers can offer both academic and emotional guidance to students is encouraged. Parents are likewise urged to build and maintain an active and healthy relationship with their children and the school to further support their educational development. Finally, it is recommended that future researchers use this study as a reference point for further exploration of topics related to parental involvement and academic performance.

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